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TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES BASED ON THE INTEGRATED EDUCATION OF EXAMPLES OF WORLD LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes modern technologies of teaching examples of world literature to students. The advantages of integrated education are emphasized.

KEYWORDS

Education, innovative technologies, integrated education, differential education.

INTRODUCTION

Active changes observed in society, constant awareness of the latest news in science is one of the necessary requirements for today's teacher. Today, in order to achieve some results in education, it is necessary to abandon traditional methods of teaching. This makes it possible to significantly increase the quality of education. Currently, students can independently improve the knowledge provided in the educational institution using the unlimited possibilities of the Internet, work on themselves, conduct scientific research, participate online in the classes of professors

and teachers working in the world's leading higher educational institutions, their they have the opportunity to be aware of the teaching techniques and the results of the research conducted in the field of science. It is known from the experience of the world that in the modern education system, teaching subjects in an integrated state, not separately, gives the expected result.

It is very important to use interdisciplinary integration in teaching literature to students. Because in literature

classes, the history of creation of literary works, style, language features, genre possibilities, writer's life, relationship with social life are analyzed. It uses external and internal integration. Literature classes require the teacher to have sufficient knowledge and skills in the fields of pedagogy, psychology, history, ethnography, culture, politics, geography, linguistics, and theology. This situation is especially evident in the analysis of works of world literature. From the literature of the ancient world to today's modern examples of literature, the human factor is at the forefront of everything. In each period, certain developments in the human mind, its psychological conditions, and social status are discussed.

It is known that ancient literature is mostly based on mythology. That is, in all the works created during this period, along with ordinary people, gods, goddesses, mythical creatures and strange creatures also play an important role in the development of events. Homer's epics "Iliad" and "Odyssey" are the most perfect sources that have reached our days. Before starting the analysis of these works with students, it is appropriate to test their knowledge in the field of ancient Greek myths, history, ethnography, geography, culture, and religious studies. Because the heroes of these works are not only people, but, as we mentioned above, Greek gods and mythical creatures. A student cannot analyze the essence of the work, its original reality, assumptions about man and the world

without sufficient knowledge in this regard. The events of the work take place in a certain place and time. The events take place mainly in Sparta in Greece and Troy in Asia Minor. It is important to know the students' opinions about these cities, their current situation, and the basic livelihood of the country's population. Because these cities are historically real places. Literary scholar H. Ismailov: - "The city of Troy was really one of the ancient cities located in Asia Minor, on the southern shore of the Dardanelles Strait. As a result of archeological research conducted by scientists a few years ago on the site of the ancient city of Troy, the ruins of a settlement that flourished nearly three thousand years before our era and later perished due to various disasters were found. Scholars say that the invasion of the Greeks on the Trojans is a historical event, and it happened around the 13th-12th century AD (1:8), he says.

It is important to use innovative methods to develop students' ability to think logically based on an integrative approach. In this process, you should pay attention to the following features:

- 1) intellectual processes, which arouse the states of thinking, reasoning, justification, proof (analysis, synthesis, generalization, comparison);
- 2) emotional processes (success, joy, pride in one's achievements, experiencing satisfaction from activity);

3) regulatory processes (volitional aspirations as a concentration of forces, goal orientation, decision-making, diligence, determination, attention);

The activities of higher education institutions in the field of pedagogy cannot be imagined without cooperation with schools. Future teachers apply the acquired knowledge in schools, and on this basis, they develop competence. Students follow the lessons of qualified teachers teaching in schools, participate in the organization of spiritual and educational events held at the school, and in creative meetings with poets and writers, they become aware of the news happening in the life of society, in the world of literature.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the advantages of teaching students based on integrated education are justified in all areas. Students will have the opportunity to acquire comprehensive knowledge, generalize their knowledge in subjects, and independently acquire new knowledge related to the field.

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